

impacts of farmer interventions on rice-invertebrate assemblages at and below the water line.

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Socioeconomics

Medicinal weeds in rice fields of Chhattisgarh, India

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We conducted an ethnobotanical survey in Raipur during 1995-98 to identify medicinal weeds in rice fields in Chhattisgarh and document their uses. The survey, undertaken in upland, medium-elevation, and lowland areas, covered all kinds of weeds. Weeds were collected and their habitat and medicinal properties were noted after identification. To determine the uses of medicinal weeds, more than 60 farmers were interviewed. Folk doctors, *tantriks* (people who practice *tantra*), *baigas* (people who cure diseases with herbal medicines, assisted by spiritual power), and Ayurvedic doctors (doctors who practice *Ayurveda*, one of India's oldest systems of medicine) were consulted on the medicinal value of weeds.

The survey revealed that more than 50 weed species infest the rice fields of Chhattisgarh. Of these, more than 35 spe-

cies have been reported in ancient Indian literature as medicinal plants. The survey also showed that Chhattisgarh farmers use more than 25 species of medicinal weeds to solve their health problems. The medicinal uses of some problematic weeds are shown in the table. The study suggested a

strong need to document valuable knowledge about medicinal weeds from experienced farmers. By knowing the medicinal uses of weeds and identifying a suitable market for them, farmers can earn extra income from these unwanted plants.

Medicinal weeds in rice fields, Chhattisgarh, India.

Weed species	Local name	Medicinal uses
<i>Cyperus scariosus</i>	Motha	For fever
<i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	Chuhaka	For stomach disorders
<i>Kyllingia monocephala</i>	Bandarphool	Anti-venom
<i>Abutilon indicum</i>	Raksi	Leaves used for bleeding piles Seeds used for treating cough
<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i>	Bhuinawla	For jaundice
<i>Eclipta alba</i>	Bhengra	For respiratory problems
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Duddhi	For respiratory problems
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Doobi	For hysteria, epilepsy, and insanity
<i>Echinochloa colonum</i>	Sawan	For stomach disorders
<i>Oxalis corniculata</i>	Khattibuti	For skin eruptions

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